

EXAMINATION MALPRACTICES IN NIGERIA: A REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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ABSTRACT

Education is the bedrock on which all human activities revolve. Examination malpractice which started unnoticed in Nigeria has become a national phenomenon and a threat to the educational system. There have been daily newspapers with screaming headlines on students' examination malpractices involving examination officials and students poor performance in academic activities. The Federal Government, Examination bodies and Researchers have proffer solutions toward curbing the vices that is plaguing our educational systems in the society. But laws and suggestions made were neither implemented nor enforced due to "Nigerian Factor". The paper recommends a change of perception by all stakeholders in order to arrest the situation.

KEYWORDS: Examination malpractice, change

INTRODUCTION

The administration of external examination known as Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) to the Senior Secondary School Students as an assessment of their six years programme that qualified them an entrance examination into tertiary institutions through Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) on minimum of five credit passes including English Language and Mathematics. The assessment examination had hitherto been handled by the West African Examination Council (WAEC) that was established in 1952 as the foremost examination board by law charged with the responsibility of determining the examinations required in the public interest in the four English speaking West African countries. To conduct the examinations and to award certificate comparable to those of equivalent examining authorities internationally before 1999, when the National Examinations Council (NECO) was established to also handle Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) for schools and private candidates in Nigeria have been fraught with problem of examination irregularities/malpractices.

The administration of external examinations first hiccup happened in 1914 when the Senior Cambridge local examinations to be conducted leaked and this scenario took a different shape when 1963, 1977, 1981 and 1987 two public examinations leaked, Uzoigwe as quoted by Olujuwon (1999).

Olujuwon (2006) opines that history had revealed that the problem of examination malpractices in Nigeria seems to be as old as the introduction of formal system of education because prior to the intervention of the colonial government in education through various ordinances, the Christian Missionaries were the first to introduce formal education in Nigeria from 1842 to 1881.

The offences are: cheating at examinations, stealing of question papers, impersonation, disturbances at examination, obstruction of supervision, forgery of result slip, breach of duty, conspiracy and aiding, etc. Government, examination bodies, and other concerned citizens have made a lot of efforts to forestall the incidences of examination malpractice and the problems associated with the conduct of examinations in Nigeria. Government, examination bodies, and other concerned citizens have made a lot of efforts to forestall the incidences of examination malpractice and the problems associated with the conduct of examinations in Nigeria. According to (Jimoh 2009) the efforts seem to be yielding some results, yet incidences of examination malpractice still feature prominently in the school system. Ojujuwon (2006) noted that measures put in place still do not deter people from engaging in examination malpractices.

In the WAEC conducted examination in 1991, 30,982 students were involved in examination malpractices while 35,479 were reported in 1992. Shonekan (1996) opines that 1992-1995 a total of 2,818,679 candidates sat for the May/June and November/December Senior School Certificate Examinations and 350,902 candidates' results were withheld for examination malpractices. Oriola (2003) reports that in 2003 JAMB (Joint Admission

and Matriculation Board) 1,099,241 sat for the examination and 116,990 candidates representing 11.5% results were withheld for various examination offences. In 2006, fourteen years after, (Jimoh 2009) states that the Federal Ministry of Education blacklisted and derecognized 324 secondary schools across the nation as centers for conducting public examinations from 2007 to 2010. The distribution of the schools that were found guilty of examination malpractice is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Examination Malpractice in Nigerian Secondary Schools

Zone	No. of Schools Involved	%
North Central	54	16.6
North East	8	2.5
North West	12	3.6
South East	48	14.8
South West	86	26.5
South South	116	36.0
TOTAL	324	100.0

Source: Week End Times, 17th & 18th February, 2007, p. 4

Graphically presented by Gbagolo H. (2011)

Table 1 shows the prevalence of examination malpractice in secondary schools in Nigeria. It occurs in all geographical zones in the country.

Ayegba (2009) reports the briefing of the Registrar of NECO, Prof. Okpala that 32,414 candidates results were either cancelled or withheld for cases of examination malpractices in 2009 Senior School Certificate Examination in which Enugu State recorded the highest of 3,742 candidates. Dr. Uwadiae (Head of the National Office (WAEC) in his media briefing to announce the release of the results of the November/December 2010 West African Senior School Certificate Examination, (WASSCE), he says a total of 324,998 candidates registered for the examination, out of which 310,077 candidates consisting of 168,835 male and 141,242 female candidates sat the examination. The results of 51,876 candidates, representing 16.73% are being withheld, based on various reports of their alleged involvement in examination malpractice.

The phenomenon of examination malpractice seems to be aggravated by the large scale and shameful involvement of dishonest and greedy teachers, school heads, parents and all those who take part in examination administration (Ijaiya, 1998). The prominence assumed by this malady in the school system has become a source of concern to stakeholders in the education industry. Every examination season witnesses new and ingenious methods of cheating. The examination process has become endangered to the extent that certification has almost lost its credibility in the country. Certificates no longer seem to reflect skill and competence. Accusing fingers have been pointed at teachers, school heads, parents, students, examination officials and even security agents as those responsible for examination malpractice in the school system (Jimoh 2009).

Examination malpractice is a social evil that can damage society to the extent of possibly leading to a failed state. It has very serious economic, political and social consequences. In the last ten years alone, the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) had to cancel the results of 814, 699 candidates in its May/June Examinations (Aminu, 2006).

DEFINITION OF EXAMINATION MALPRACTICE

Various eggheads have attempted to define it from different perspectives. According to Shonekan (1996) as any act of omission or commission that contravenes the Rules and Regulations of the examination body to the extent of undermining the validity and reliability of the tests and ultimately, the integrity of the certificates issued. Ahmed (1993) sees it as any act of wrong doing or neglect that contravenes the rules of acceptable practices before, during and after an examination by any body in any way tantamount to malpractices. Salami (1994) defines examination malpractice as an improper and dishonest act associated with examination with a view to obtaining unmerited advantage. Argungu (1997) defined examination malpractice as any irregularity which is premeditated and perpetrated by candidates or their agents with the intention of gaining undue advantage over others in an examination. Jega (2006) saw examination malpractice as any form of misbehaviour that leads to the alteration of or a tempering with the prescribed ways of conducting examination in any given system. Any act of omission or commission which compromises the validity, reliability and integrity of any assessment or evaluation system (i.e. the violation of, or disregard for examination ethics (Obo, 2008).

The definitions above revealed that examination malpractice is an unwelcome phenomenon to the administration of external examinations because it is detrimental to the growth and development of education in any society. The standard of education in Nigeria has taken a nosedive according to expert and unhealthy situation to a developing nation like Nigeria who requires the contributions of its nationals in the building of a virile economy.

FORMS OF EXAMINATION MALPRACTICE

1. Impersonation: Entails the hiring of touts to write examinations by appearing in the halls as the genuine candidates. Uzoigwe (2000) states that male candidates sitting in for girls and vice versa in some sensitive papers, twins writing examinations for each other in connivance with the school examination officers/invigilators or supervisors and other examination officials.

2. Collusion: Arises when an assigned invigilator or supervisor receiving or giving assistance to candidates in the examination hall for gratification,

3. Examination leakages: A situation where question papers are seen by candidates prior to the writing of the examinations and are traceable to the printing press or persons connected with the custody of the question papers.

4 Mass cheating: Is traceable to large scale organized cheating involving school authorities, examination officials and candidates through the answering of the questions on the chalkboard for the candidates to copy.

5 Smuggling of answer scripts: Involves candidates having external assistance to take to and fro the examination hall answer scripts duly prepared by syndicates in connivance with invigilators and/or supervisors and other examination officials.

6 Dubbing: An arrangement involving the invigilators or supervisors whereby candidates are allowed to copy from each other in the hall.

7 Insult/Assault on Supervisors/Invigilators/Inspectors by candidates: Takes the form of beating of examination officials, destruction of examination officials' cars and manhandling of examination officials and/or using indecent language on supervisors and invigilators who fail to cooperate with them.

8 Bringing foreign materials into the examination hall: Such as textbooks, cribs, past questions papers either containing copious notes or used as disguise for current ones that have been smuggled out, photocopies of prepared answers.

And the writer would like to add the followings:

9 Procurement of answer booklets: This is one of the ways the syndicate operates; whereby they have enough current answer booklets through the assistance of the examination body personnel. They tactically exchange written answer booklets with their candidates before stoppage time and/or in connivance with the school examination officer and the assigned supervisor.

10 Enrolling syndicate and self: This happens during the enrolment, the syndicate will be enrolled alongside with the candidate using fake names. In the examination hall, the syndicate will be doing the writing and at the end exchange answer booklet with the candidate.

11 Late submissions of parcels by the Supervisor: The custodian in agreement with some assigned supervisors submits their parcels late. This arrangement gives the supervisors and touts enough time to complete their writings and rearrangement of the scripts. The custodian is settled after receiving the parcels.

CAUSES OF EXAMINATION MALPRACTICE

The experts have identified the following as some of the causes and their views were corroborated by Jimoh (2009):

- Immorality in the wider society: The high corruption in the Nigerian society has given rise to unprecedented things to happen without questioning. Young boys and girls offer money and/or themselves for sex in order to pass examinations. They often used ungodly maxims 'join them if you cannot beat them' and at such use what you have to get what you need.
- Inadequate supervision of teachers by inspectors: Due to the poor remuneration of teachers and nonchalant attitudes of the civil servants, programs of supervisions on every term are not religiously followed and teachers capitalize on these lapses to avoid classes. Also, the schedule of their inspections are made known to the teachers who prepared lesson notes ahead of their visits both on topics taught and not.
- High enrolment fees: There have been increases in examination fees on yearly basis and parents and students alike do all they could to avoid re-enrolment.
- Tying of promotion of teachers to success of candidates in public examinations: This practice has give rise to every subject teachers to be actively involve in the conduct of their subject paper during examinations in order not to jeopardize their promotion.
- The desire of our students and parents for success at all cost: When parents determined courses for their children while undermining their intellectuality and the advice of a Guidance and Counselor, such parent spend money to see their children qualified for their choice of course.
- Poor teaching in schools: There have been brain drain in the country due to poor remuneration and misplacement of teaching profession in our society, the aftermath is shortages of qualified teachers. The available teachers were made to teach subjects outside their areas of specialization.
- Non-completion of syllabus before examination: Teachers are prepared to teach but students refuses to attend classes and thus lead to the abandonment of teaching and non completion of examination syllabus because of the students' perception about examinations.
- Lack of confidence on the part of teachers and students: Due to shortages of qualified teachers, most students believed on the external assistance they will receive during the examinations. While the teachers not too sure on the ability of the students to discharge what they have been taught, offered to assist in order to have credible numbers of passes in his/her subject.
- Absence of guidance and counseling services in schools: This has been a bane to the growth and development of our educational system. Due to the prospect or high pay in the Petroleum Industries, every student want to be involved in petroleum related courses whether bright or dull academically because of the absence guidance and counseling officers in schools.

Gbenedio (1993) added the followings

- Constant closure of schools: This has weakened academic excellence in schools because of disruption of academic calendars due to strikes
- Over-emphasis on examinations and certificate: This emphasis has given rise to examination malpractices because academic excellence, skills and competency are sacrificed on the altar of certificate
- Poor living condition: Poor remuneration of supervisors and other examination officials by the examination bodies give rise to examination malpractice.

Olujuwon (2006) put forward the followings:

- Over crowding in the school, for example 1 teacher to 83 – 100 pupils.
- Parental contributions for example, some parents pay for live papers and hire people to sit for examination on behalf of their wards.

Writing in the same vein, Badmus (2006), Awanbor (2005), Nwandiani (2005), Okafor (2006), Ayua (2006), Azare (2006) and Aminu (2006) identified school programmes, teaching learning environment, the teacher, the student, over value of certificates, decadence in the Nigerian society and parental support are some of the factors responsible for examination malpractice.

The writer adds:

- Fear of students' drift by the public school: The headships of public schools are afraid of losing their students to the private schools and so connive with the school examination officer and teachers to assist the students to cheat during examinations.

PERPETRATORS OF EXAMINATION MALPRACTICE

According to Olujuwon (2006) quoting Aina (1993), Mahmoud (1993) and Bunza (1993) identified the underlisted as the perpetrators of examination malpractices.

1. Government Officials, Institutions
2. Parents/guardians
3. Teachers/Head Teachers
4. Lazy students

EFFORTS

1. BY THE GOVERNMENT

Examination malpractice is a cankerworm that has eaten into the heart of Nigerian students and the embarrassing frequent WAEC examination papers leakages, forced the Federal Government to take a decisive action to curb examination malpractices. The promulgation of decree 27 of 1973, Miscellaneous Decree 20 of 1984 and Act No. 33 of May, 1999 titled 'Examination Malpractice Decree' reversed the decree but stipulated punishment ranging from a fine of N50,000 to N100,000 and imprisonment for a term of 3 – 4 years with or without option of fine.

BLACKLIST STUDENTS, SCHOOLS

The Federal Government through Minister of State for Education, Barr Wike Nyesom decried the rate of examination malpractice among students at various levels that both teachers and students had been affected. The President has inaugurated a task force on education that will also examine all laws militating against the delivery of qualitative education and purpose necessary changes. Conclusively, he says, that government has also resolved to blacklist any student or schools involved in examination malpractice (Vanguard Newspaper 2011).

2. BY THE EXAMINATION BODIES

Prior to the establishment of National Examinations Council (NECO) by the Federal Government for Nigerians, West African Examination Council (WAEC) has been a lonely voice in the struggle against examination malpractices/irregularities. Some of the strategies introduced by the body to arrest examination malpractice are as follows:

- **EMBOSSMENT OF CERTIFICATES** – The frequent incidence of examination malpractices of which one of the factors was impersonation, only WAEC has introduced passport photograph embossment on certificates issued to successful candidates.

- **CANDIDATE FORMS** – The examination bodies make available in book form and on its website to intending candidates for examination, the rules and regulations and the punishment thereof of different offences.

- **PUBLIC AWARENESS** – The examination bodies have launched several campaigns to sensitize the public of the danger in examination malpractices. The campaign according to Uzoigwe (2000) gave rise to Examination Ethics.

- **SECURITY BAGS** – As a precautionary measure, the bodies also introduced the use of security bags by all assigned supervisors with the School Authority and WAEC/NECO staff at the custodian point in possession of the keys only. The essence is to prevent the tampering with the question papers and answer booklets while in-transit.

- **SANCTIONS** – The bodies sanction candidates involved in examination malpractices by withholding their results, staff of the examination bodies involved are dismissed while teachers and other examination officials are reported to their employers for appropriate measure. In the 49th NEC meeting of WAEC held in Ibadan, the

council resolved to publish list of indicted supervisors and invigilators involved in examination malpractices (Ekudugho 2011)

- EXAMINATION MATERIALS – The examination bodies ensure that examination question papers are delivered to the custodian point daily for onward distributions to examination centers through the appointed supervisors.

- APPOINTMENT OF EXAMINATION SUPERVISORS – To enhance discipline and compliance with directives, examination centre supervisors are recommended by the Ministry of Education and when appointed, the bodies ensure that they are swapped on daily basis to avoid undue influence by the schools.

3. RELIGIOUS BODIES

Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) held education summit asking the government to tackle examination malpractice through special court (Sunday Trust 2010). The essence is to enhance speedy dispensation of justice and avoidance of miscarriage of justice.

4. SCHOLARS/RESEACHERS

Jimoh (2009) proffers the followings.

1. Sincere Implementation of Legislation by Government and Other Agencies. He advocated that since the enacted laws are not enforceable due to *Nigerian factor*, a special commission be created namely 'Examination Malpractice Commission' to enhance speed dispensation of justice.
2. Empowerment of Teachers
3. Less Emphasis on Certificates and Paper Qualification
4. Improved Funding of the Education Sector
5. Campaigns and Seminars on the Dangers of Examination Malpractice
6. Special Welfare Package for Examination Officials

Others are:

1. The number of invigilators and supervisors should be increased in the exam halls.
2. Apart from photographs, finger prints on certificates should be used for identification
3. Planting of secret cameras in the examination halls. Abdulwahab (2004)
4. Moral Upbringing of Children.
5. Public Enlightenment Advocacy by the Media.
6. Re-orientation in our Tertiary Institutions and Better Funding.
7. Integrity Watch for Business, Community and Political Leaders.
8. Job Creation and Good Governance

RECOMMENDATIONS

Uzoigwe (2000) opines that no one can claim to have all the solutions to the eradication of examination malpractice. The following recommendations are proffered to help in curbing the ugly trend that is plaguing our nation educational foundation.

1. OFFICIAL REMUNERATION - An attractive remuneration to examination officials and centre supervisors will motivate them to discharge their duties creditably well. The current allowance payable to a centre supervisor for a period of one month that the examination will last is currently below six digits, plus other expenses (transportation to and fro Custodian Point and to and fro assigned examination centers and feeding is less than N40,00.00) is too meager and thus creates rooms for corrupt practices by officials. The amount should be reviewed upward.
2. TRANSPORTATION - The idea of allowing the centre supervisors and other examination officials to foot their transportation bills throughout the days of the examination makes room for compromise. Cost of transportation and feeding should be worked out and made available to centre supervisors and other examination officials on daily basis to forestall undue influence and compromise.
3. DISCONTINUATION OF EVERY SCHOOL AS CENTERS –The idea of using every school as examination centre has to a large extent hampered effective monitoring of external examinations by the appointed monitoring teams/staff of the examination bodies. Some local government areas have over 25 public secondary schools outside privately owned. Therefore, monitoring teams spent less than 15 minutes in a centre in order to cover many schools within the time allocated to such subject, thereafter

TABLE 2: FORMS, CAUSES, PERPETRATOR AND EFFORTS OF EXAMINATION MALPRACTICE

FORMS	CAUSES	PERPETRATORS	EFFORTS
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Impersonation 2. Collusion 3. Examination leakages 4. Mass cheating 5. Smuggling of answer scripts. 6. Dubbing. 7. Insult/Assault on supervisors/invigilators/inspectors by candidates. 8. Bringing foreign materials into the examination halls. 9. Procurement of answer booklets. 10. Enrolling syndicate and self. 11. Late submission of parcels by the supervisor. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Immorality in the wider society. 2. Inadequate supervision of teachers by inspectors. 3. High enrolment fees 4. Tying of promotion of teachers success of candidates in public examinations. 5. The desire of our students and parents for success at all cost. 6. Poor teaching in schools. 7. Non-completion of syllabus before examination 8. Lack of confidence on the part of teachers and students. 9. Absence of guidance and counseling services in schools. 10. Constant closure of schools. 11. Over-emphasis on examination and certificate. 12. Poor living condition. 13. Feat of students' drift by the public school. 	<p>Government Officials, Institutions Parents/guardians Teachers/Head Teachers Lazy students</p>	<p>BY THE GOVERNMENT</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Promulgation of Decree and Act . 2. Blacklist Students, Schools. <p>BY THE EXAMINATION BODIES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Embossment of Certificates 2. Candidate Forms 3. Public Awareness 4. Security Bags 5. Sanctions 6. Examination Materials 7. Appointment of Examination Supervisors <p>RELIGIOUS BODIES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Creation of Special Court <p>SCHOLARS/RESEARCHER:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sincere Implementation of Legislation by Government and Other Agencies 2. Empowerment of Teachers 3. Less Emphasis on Certificates and Paper Qualification 4. Improved Funding of the Education Sector 5. Campaigns and Seminars on the Dangers of Examination Malpractice 6. Special Welfare Package for Examination Officials 7. The number of invigilators and supervisors should be increased in the exam halls. 8. Apart from photographs, finger prints on certificates should be used for identification. 9. Planting of secret cameras in the examination halls. 10. Moral Upbringing of Children. 11. Public Enlightenment Advocacy by the Media. 12. Re-orientation in our Tertiary Institutions and Better Funding. 13. Integrity Watch for Business, Community and Political Leaders. 14. Job Creation and Good Governance

4. their illegal business continues. Centers should be created randomly in local government areas and the bodies prepared schedules schools to be covered by each centers within the local government with daily monitoring team posted to such centers.
5. RESTRICTED WEBSITE – The examination bodies should ensure that they have a restricted website inaccessible to the public to avoid examination paper leakages as access to their website during examinations.
6. PRINTING PRESS – The examination bodies should endeavor to have their own printing press to handle the printing of question papers/answer booklets to prevent examination paper leakages. Also, the staff should be searched daily in the course of printing question papers and all waste sheets of papers shredded.

CONCLUSION

The administration of external examinations to all secondary school leavers throughout the country is not a small task but hinge on proper planning, the first functions of management. Though, the examination bodies are faced with other challenges as summarized by researchers as follows:

(1) Poor funding, (2) Inadequate staff, (3) Existing Laws, (4) Degradation of Moral Values, (5) Problems Posed by ICT and (6) Increasing Risk to Life. In contribution, Jimoh (2009) and Olujuwon (2006) opine that Anomie is what had sustained examination malpractices in Nigeria.

The challenges are much and but my findings have revealed that the problem of examination malpractices/irregularities involved all stakeholders but with higher problems emanating from the examination bodies and exacerbated by corruption. Lately, WAEC caused confusion in the country by two contradictory results released in respect of WASSCE May/June, 2011, one in August 10, 2011 and thereafter three weeks later. The explanation adduced by the body, the WASSCE May/June, 2011 results were released with some pending/outstanding and there was need to update some outstanding results. According to the body that due to human error traced to yet-to-be identified staff the result update altered the already released results (Edukugho 2011). What an embarrassing situation?

The laws and recommendations/suggestions by all stakeholders have to be implemented to form the bedrock of 'conduct of examinations' policy by the examination bodies and administered by all organs saddle with the responsibility to bring about improve standard of education in Nigeria. The wind of change will bring a shift in response to the true management of the policy, and then the shift will cause things to fall apart for good of the educational system and the Nigerian society.

Therefore all stakeholders must be alive to their responsibility through effective management and full implementation of all the recommendations/suggestions to curb the ugly monster.

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Received for Publication: 02/10 /2011

Accepted for Publication: 10/12 /2011